

POLY-VICTIMIZATION, INTERNALIZING AND EXTERNALIZING BEHAVIORAL PROBLEMS IN INDIVIDUALS WITH INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENTAL DISORDER

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship in poly-victimization and internalizing as well as externalizing behavioral problems in individuals with Intellectual Developmental Disorder (IDD). A purposive sample of 120 participants aged 18–25, formally diagnosed with IDD, was recruited from clinical and special education settings. Standardized instruments assessed victimization experiences and behavioral problems. Correlational analyses revealed that higher poly-victimization was significantly correlated with greater internalizing (e.g., anxiety, depression) and externalizing behavioral problems (e.g., aggression, impulsivity). Among subtypes, peer victimization consistently emerged as the strongest predictor of both internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems. Regression analysis identified peer victimization as the main predictor of anxiety and depression, while child maltreatment and male gender predicted impulsivity. Exposure to crime was linked to antisocial behavior and increased hypersensitivity, whereas sexual victimization unexpectedly showed an inverse relationship with hypersensitivity. A positive father–child relationship was related with fewer depressive symptoms, highlighting its potential protective role. These findings underscore the cumulative and multidimensional psychological effects of poly-victimization in individuals with IDD and highlight the need for trauma-informed care, family engagement, and context-sensitive interventions tailored to low-resource settings. The study contributes novel evidence to inform future policy, screening, and support services for vulnerable populations in collectivistic cultures.

Introduction

Individuals with intellectual developmental disorders (IDD) represent some of the most marginalized and vulnerable groups in society (Emerson & Hatton, 2007; Hughes et al., 2012). Though cognitive and adaptive impairments in these individuals are well known, emotional injuries they may sustain, particularly those caused by victimization, often go unnoticed. Research

from across the world informs that individuals with disabilities are far more likely to be subjected to forms of abuse, neglect, and peer victimization compared to typically developing peers (WHO, 2022; UNICEF, 2021). Jones et al. (2012), in a meta-analysis, reported, that individuals with disabilities are 3.7 times as likely to be victims of violence as a whole, and the most common is

emotional abuse. In U.S, 28% of individuals with developmental disabilities say they experience bullying, in comparison with 12% of neuro typical ones (CDC, 2023). In Pakistan, even with broad-scale data being limited, present studies suggest that over 60% of individuals with disabilities experienced at least one form of victimization, often in the form of a family or school environment (Mahmood et al., 2020). This trend of increasing poly-victimization, experiencing multiple forms of abuse, such as physical, emotional, sexual, or peer violence, has a strong psychological impact, particularly in the case of individuals with IDD who experience difficulty in understanding or communicating emotional suffering. These experiences in such cases usually become internalizing behavior problems (e.g., depression, anxiety) or externalizing behavior problems (e.g., impulsivity, aggressiveness). Grasping this relationship is vital to the formation of appropriate intervention strategies within populations where emotional pain tends to remain concealed because of communicative and cognitive deficits, especially within individuals with intellectual developmental disorders (IDD).

Intellectual Developmental Disorder (IDD)

Intellectual Developmental Disorder (IDD) is a developmental condition with impairment in intellectual functioning, as well as in adaptive behavior, appearing earlier in life. Traditionally, it has been called mental retardation, but it has been deemed stigmatizing, with professional organizations like the American Association on Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities (AAIDD) advocating updating terminology, resulting in today's use of Intellectual Developmental Disorder (Schalock et al., 2007). According to DSM-5-TR, IDD has impairments in intellectual areas like reasoning and problem-solving, and adaptive functioning across conceptual, social, as well as practical domain (APA, 2022). Severity is categorized into four levels as mild, moderate, severe and profound, depending on degrees of support for daily living, not IQ alone. Understanding this clinical framework is essential before examining its

epidemiological patterns across global and regional contexts.

Intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD) affect approximately 1% to 3% of individuals worldwide, with region-specific differences because of access to medical attention, socioeconomic factors, and environmental exposures (Maulik et al., 2011; McKenzie et al., 2016). Latest estimates suggest that over 107 million individuals worldwide have intellectual disability (Olusanya et al., 2022). For Asia, the estimate is between 1.5% and 2.5%, demonstrating regional distribution (Durkin et al., 2007). For Pakistan, there is an estimate of around about 2% and 2.5% among its population base, even if with potential shortcomings because of constrained workup infrastructure for diagnosis and social stigma and limited public awareness (Zahoor et al., 2022; Mirza et al., 2009; Khan et al., 2012). This epidemiological observation necessarily follows scrutiny on how IDD reveals itself clinically.

Clinically, individuals with IDD exhibit delayed developmental milestones, communication disability, and adaptive behavior deficits like social interaction and self-care. These deficits also entail problems at school together with social interactions and thereby provide an origin for emotional and behavioral issues like aggression, social withdrawal, anxiety, and irritability (Matson & Shoemaker, 2009). In light of this clinical complexity, there is a need to investigate theoretical frameworks to account for the social and cognitive challenges seen among these individuals, establishing the basis for practical intervention measures based on theory.

Poly-Victimization

The understanding of poly victimization has evolved significantly, moving beyond early frameworks that emphasized singular, isolated forms of harm. Increasingly, research recognizes that individuals, particularly those from marginalized or vulnerable populations such as individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD), often experience multiple, co-occurring forms of victimization across various contexts (Finkelhor, 2008; Hughes et al., 2012).

These may include interpersonal violence, institutional abuse, community violence, and systemic neglect (Fisher et al., 2016; Hatton et al., 2015). This broader perspective highlights that victimization is rarely a one-time or isolated event, but often part of a complex pattern of repeated and overlapping exposures to harm throughout an individual's life (Turner et al., 2010; Mikton et al., 2014). Cicchetti & Lynch (1993) proposed the ecological-transactional model, highlighting how different kinds of risk factors in family, school, and community systems operate together in increasing exposure to abuse.

Poly-victimization is also termed as a combination of different types of abuse and violence in a one's life, including physical abuse, sexual victimization, bullying, as well as domestic violence witnessed (Finkelhor et al. 2007). In contrast with single victimization experiences, poly-victimization has more severe, longer-term psychological consequences. In individuals with intellectual developmental disorders (IDD), rates are even higher, with studies as high as 3 times greater than comparable peers with no intellectual developmental disorders (Jones et al., 2012).

Types of Poly-Victimization

Finkelhor's (2007) model identifies five broad areas of poly-victimization. First is conventional crime victimization, including physical assault, robbery, and attempted abduction. For individuals with IDD, limited safety knowledge could particularly make them susceptible for such incidents. The second is child maltreatment, including physical abuse, neglect, psychological abuse, and custodial interference, committed commonly by caregivers. Third is peer/sibling victimization, including bullying or physical fights, disproportionately experienced by individuals with developmental disabilities in school and home environments due to deficits in social skills (OJJDP, 2009). Fourth is sexual victimization, from harassment to sexual violence, with individuals with IDD particularly being at risk due to impaired ability to detect as well as disclose sexual misconduct. Finally, witnessing victimization is witnessing violence within or outside one's home. IDD individuals might not be

capable of processing or describing these incidents, making them even more traumatized. Even though these five types already cover a broad spectrum, newer dangers like cyberbullying and online abuse are being acknowledged as new landscapes of danger, particularly because technology has become more accessible even for individuals with intellectual disabilities (UNICEF, 2021). Given the complexity and intensity of these victimization types, it becomes essential to study their patterns and prevalence among individuals with IDD within the framework of trauma epidemiology.

Theoretical Framework

Finkelhor (2007) Poly-Victimization model offers a systematic framework for how some individuals are subjected to multiple types of victimization instead of a one-time occurrence. From a developmental victimology perspective, it emphasizes how experiences of harm are impacted by their individual vulnerabilities, and environmental circumstances.

Poly-victimization, according to Finkelhor, is not random, it emerges through identifiable pathways that heighten risk across domains such as home, school, peer groups, and the broader community.

The initial pathway is dangerous families, in which violence, abuse, or neglect fails to adequately shield individuals from harm and subjects them to further harm in other environments. A second pathway, chaotic households and family disruption, delves into how separation between individuals' parents, economic deprivation, or frequent caregiver change brings instability, making it more difficult for individuals to be protected, leading to repeated victimizations. Third, individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD) who experience emotional difficulties such as anxiety, depression, or behavioral problems, and who often struggle with communication and social skills, are more likely to attract negative attention and may become easier targets for victimization. Lastly, dangerous or disadvantaged places like violent neighborhoods, under-resourced schools, or institution-based care environments raise levels of exposure to crime, bullying, and exploitation.

This model is particularly relevant to this current study since individuals with IDD have cognitive limitations, are even more caregiver-dependent, and have limited capacity for recognizing or reporting abuse, increasing all four pathways' vulnerability. These processes explain how poly-victimization leads to internalizing (e.g., depression, anxiety) as well as externalizing (e.g., defiance, aggression) problems in this population, forming a theoretically informed framework for understanding behavior outcomes (Finkelhor, 2007).

Behavioral Problems

Behavioral problems have long been recognized as a clear and significant concern in both clinical and developmental contexts. Initially, behavior problems were thought to be largely identified based on overt behavioral disturbances such as disobedience, aggression, and outbursts of temper and referred to as "misbehavior" or poor discipline (Kazdin, 1987). With experience, research escalated to the identification of the fact that behavioral patterns were not only environmental but could actually have an etiology related to emotional, neurological, and developmental dysfunctions, especially among those with cognitive deficits (Hinshaw, 1992). Around the same time, clinicians became sensitized to individuals who suffer not outwardly but internally, with too much fear, sadness, or withdrawal, the symptoms of internal suffering largely overlooked due to their lesser tendency to openly express themselves (Achenbach & Edelbrock, 1983). Eventually, dichotomization of behavioral issues of individuals into two broad dimensions became widespread consensus as externalizing and internalizing behavioral problems. Externalizing behavior constitutes outward-oriented behavior such as aggression, defiance, and impulsiveness, while internalizing behavior constitutes inner-focused symptoms such as anxiety, hypersensitivity, and depression.

Internalizing Behavioral Problems

Individuals with Intellectual Developmental Disorder (IDD) are particularly susceptible to internalizing problems due to limited verbal

expression, compromised coping mechanisms, and increased exposure to negative social interaction. Empirical research suggests that delays in neurodevelopment hinder emotional regulation, making them more likely to show enhanced anxiety, depression, and emotional hypersensitivity (Dekker & Koot, 2003; Emerson, 2003). Frequent exposure to adverse experiences such as exclusion, bullying, and abuse can heighten psychic disturbance, particularly when they cannot express or control emotions in normal modes (Sullivan & Knutson, 2000).

Among internalizing behavioral problems, anxiety is highly prevalent (Merikangas et al., 2010), presenting as restlessness, avoidance, worrying, and somatic complaints. Depression in individuals with IDD is also a significant concern; instead of verbalized sadness, they may become irritable, withdrawn, tired, or show sleep or appetite disturbances (Einfeld & Tonge, 1996). Consistent exposure to negative social experiences and limited affective support further increases risk for depressive symptoms (Gadow et al., 2005). These symptoms often go undetected due to atypical presentation.

Another key element is hypersensitivity, involving heightened emotional responsiveness and low frustration tolerance. Sensory or interpersonal hypersensitivity is common in IDD and increases susceptibility to internalizing negative affect. Matson & Shoemaker (2009) assert that heightened emotional responsiveness can be both a symptom and a predictor of internalizing behavior.

Internalizing problems rarely occur alone. Literature shows that individuals exposed to poly-victimization, ongoing and diverse patterns of abuse, are significantly more likely to exhibit internalizing symptoms (Finkelhor et al., 2007). In individuals with IDD, who face increased risks for maltreatment, poly-victimization magnifies emotional suffering and leads to severe internalizing impairments (OJJDP, 2023; WHO, 2022). Due to limited coping mechanisms and high exposure to adversity, internalizing pathology in IDD often remains undetected and untreated, especially in low-resource and high-stigma environments. Emotional dysregulation and

unresolved trauma may spill over into externalizing behaviors such as aggression, impulsivity, and defiance, illustrating how cumulative trauma shapes developmental outcomes.

Externalizing Behavioral Problems

Externalizing behavioral problems involve maladaptive responses directed outward, including aggression, defiance, impulsivity, hyperactivity, and antisocial behavior (Achenbach & Edelbrock, 1983). Unlike internalizing problems, they are visible and readily noticed by parents, teachers, and clinicians. The Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL) classified behavioral problems into internalizing and externalizing dimensions, emphasizing their identification and intervention (Achenbach & Edelbrock, 1983).

Prevalence varies globally: 6–15% in high-income countries, 5–10% in parts of Asia, and 8–12% in Pakistan (Polanczyk et al., 2015; Imran et al., 2018; Rabbani et al., 2010). Males, especially in low-income populations, are more likely to exhibit these behaviors.

Historically, early research identified defiance and aggression as indicators of behavioral deviance (Healy & Bronner, 1926; Quay, 1965). Later models incorporated biopsychosocial factors, showing how temperament, parenting, and environmental stressors interact to influence externalizing behaviors (Frick et al., 1993). These behaviors are now understood as multifactorial, shaped by both individual vulnerabilities and contextual factors.

Cultural and Religious Context

In collectivist, religious, and traditional Asian cultures such as Pakistan, individuals with intellectual developmental disorder (IDD) are highly vulnerable to poly-victimization due to stigma, low awareness, and traditional thinking (Hameed & Manzoor, 2016; Miles, 2002). Disability is often misunderstood and linked with shame or supernatural causes, leading to concealment, negligence, or culturally justified abuse (Mirza & Hassan, 2006). Although joint family systems may offer support, they can also expose individuals with IDD to peer aggression

and emotional abuse within the household (Yousafzai et al., 2011). These harms accumulate and result in internalizing symptoms such as sadness, anxiety, and withdrawal, as well as externalizing behaviors like aggression, hyperactivity, and defiance (Emerson & Hatton, 2007; Jones et al., 2012).

In contrast, Islamic teachings emphasize dignity, mercy, and protection for individuals with disabilities, strictly prohibiting abuse and injustice (Ghaly, 2010). Religious guidance urges caregivers and society to treat vulnerable individuals with kindness and respect. Thus, while cultural norms may increase risk, religious teachings advocate for the protections aligned with ethical and psychological well-being.

In conclusion, poly-victimization severely affects individuals with IDD due to their heightened vulnerability and limited coping skills. Theoretical models such as Finkelhor's victimization pathways, ecological-transactional theory, trauma theory, and social learning theory explain how repeated trauma leads to internalizing problems (anxiety, depression, withdrawal) and externalizing behaviors (aggression, defiance, impulsivity). In Pakistan, factors like poverty, stigma, lack of awareness, and weak reporting systems intensify these outcomes, with internalizing symptoms often missed and externalizing behaviors misattributed to the disorder. Effective support requires trauma-informed, culturally sensitive interventions, caregiver training, inclusive education, and addressing cultural and religious barriers to ensure safety, dignity, and psychological well-being.

Literature Review

This chapter overviews past research concerning poly-victimization and its linkage with internalizing and externalizing behavior problems among individuals who have intellectual developmental disorder (IDD). The review is centered on the effects of exposure to several types of victimization in the behavioral outcome among this group of individuals, with special emphasis on psychosocial and neurodevelopmental factors. The review integrates empirical evidence for the given parameters, as well as family and societal

environments of individuals with IDD. Through the analysis of previous research studies, the current knowledge is put into perspective, gaps are

determined, and the provision of basis for the understanding of the intricate relationships for the current research is enabled.

Author(s)	Year	Method / Design	Main Results / Findings
Codina et al.	2020	Cross-sectional; convenience purposive sampling of 260 adults; Juvenile Victimization Questionnaire	96.9% experienced victimization; high rates of common crimes (87.7%), witnessing (67.3%), caregiver abuse (59.2%), sexual victimization (35%), and poly-victimization (13+ types). Younger adults and women were more vulnerable.
Díaz-Faes, Codina & Pereda	2024	Latent class analysis on cross-sectional self-report data from 260 participants	Identified 3 victimization patterns: high (10.4%), medium (37.3%), low (52.3%). High group (mostly females) showed greater sexual and physical abuse; variability across gender, education, residence, and support needs.
Sterling et al.	2021	Archival clinician-reported data; n = 502 (ages 4-18); interRAI ChYMH-DD (2012-2020)	64.7% experienced at least one PTE; 33% experienced poly-victimization. Poly-victimization, male sex, and mild/moderate IDD predicted higher externalizing behaviors; nonlinear age-symptom relationship.
Ferrara et al.	2021	Literature review on trauma and neurodevelopmental disorders	Exposure to violence correlates with ADHD, ASD, and learning disabilities. Both direct and indirect trauma linked to behavioral disturbances, exacerbated by socioeconomic factors. Neurobiological consequences remain understudied.
Ford et al.	2018	Editorial summary of six empirical studies	Poly-victimization has multifaceted, long-term biopsychosocial consequences. Emphasized comprehensive research and clinical strategies; did not present new data.

MacDonald et al.	2021	Case file review; n = 117 (ages 3-18); clinical sample	Poly-victimized individuals had more financial stress, parental abuse, and parental mental health issues. Higher trauma symptoms, but regression showed no significant link after adjustment. Highlighted need for screening multiple abuses.
Müller et al.	2022	Cross-sectional online survey; n = 226 youth (OOHC vs. biological families); self & caregiver reports	OOHC youth had higher poly-victimization and internalizing problems. For biological families, internalizing problems mediated poly-victimization → bullying victimization. OOHC showed direct effects.
Roca et al.	2016	Multiple regression; n = 144 adolescents receiving mental health services	Poly-victimization, non-productive coping, and low support predicted internalizing symptoms. Coping mediated the relationship.
Finkelhor et al.	2020	Systematic review of 22 studies (JVQ)	Poly-victimization linked to higher internalizing and externalizing symptoms than any single victimization type. Highlighted need for longitudinal research and prevention strategies.
Becker et al.	2021	Cross-sectional; n = 78 adolescents with ADHD; self and parent questionnaires	In-person victimization → anxiety; cyber victimization → parent-reported depression. Both associated with lower self-esteem. Poly-victimized adolescents had the most severe symptoms.
Elsaesser et al.	2018	Latent profile analysis; n = 1,196 students (grades 8-10); standardized surveys	Five profiles identified. Victims of frequent bullying showed high internalizing-externalizing symptom combinations. Outdated dataset but valuable insights.

Brown et al.	2021	Archival clinical intake data; n = 502 youth (ages 4-18); interRAI ChYMHD-DD	64.7% had PTEs; 33% poly-victimized. Poly-victimization, mild/moderate IDD, and male gender associated with more externalizing symptoms.
Fuentes et al.	2017	Cross-sectional; n = 78 adolescents under child protection services in Chile	Poly-victimization predicted externalizing behavior. Seeking social support buffered this effect, acting as a protective factor.
Heleniak et al.	2018	Cross-sectional; n = 84 foster children aged 3-4; EF & behavior measures	Poly-victimized children with low EF showed severe externalizing problems; average or high EF acted as resilience factor.
Van Nieuwenhuijzen et al.	2009	Correlational study; n = 186 individuals aged 12-14 with mild ID/BIF; video-based social problem-solving tasks	Externalizing behavior correlated with poor encoding, aggressive responses, and negative assertiveness attitudes. Emphasized mismatch between cognitive competence and real-life behavior.
Baker et al.	2015	Longitudinal study; n = 169; ages 3-18; person-centered analyses	Maternal depression and family impact predicted adverse behavior trajectories. Maternal sensitivity linked to better externalizing outcomes. Emphasized early family interventions.

Significance of the Study, Aims & Hypotheses

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its focus on the under-researched area of poly-victimization among individuals with intellectual developmental disorder (IDD) in a low-resource, collectivist cultural context such as Pakistan. While global research has increasingly recognized the serious psychological and behavioral effects of exposure to multiple forms of victimization, most existing evidence is drawn from high-income, Western contexts. There remains a notable gap in empirical research from developing countries,

where factors such as poverty, stigma, lack of diagnostic infrastructure, and traditional cultural attitudes exacerbate the risks faced by individuals with IDD. In Pakistan, individuals with IDD are at a heightened risk of multiple victimizations due to their social marginalization, limited communication abilities, and inadequate protective systems. Yet, empirical evidence on the prevalence, nature, and consequences of poly-victimization in this group remains scarce. Emotional and behavioral problems, which can often be attributed to developmental disability alone, may in fact be significantly shaped by

repeated traumatic experiences that remain unrecognized and untreated. By examining the relationship between poly-victimization and both internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems, this study aims to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the psychological vulnerabilities of individuals with IDD. Furthermore, identifying the types of victimization most strongly associated with specific behavioral outcomes can inform the development of targeted, trauma-informed interventions and policy responses. The study's findings are expected to have practical implications for clinical practice, special education, and family support services, particularly in low-resource settings. By highlighting the role of family relationships and protective factors, the research can also guide culturally appropriate intervention strategies that leverage religious and community resources.

Aims of the Study

1. To examine the relationship between poly-victimization and internalizing behavioral problems (such as anxiety, depression, hypersensitivity) among individuals with intellectual developmental disorder (IDD).
2. To examine the relationship between poly-victimization and externalizing behavioral problems (such as aggression, impulsivity, and antisocial behaviors) among individuals with intellectual developmental disorder (IDD).

3. To explore the differential contribution of types of victimization (peer victimization, child maltreatment, sexual victimization, exposure to crime) to various internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems.

4. To investigate the role of family relationship variables (such as father-child relationship) in moderating internalizing and externalizing behavioral outcomes among individuals with IDD.

Hypotheses

1. **H1:** There will be a significant positive relationship between poly-victimization and internalizing behavioral problems in individuals with IDD.
2. **H2:** There will be a significant positive relationship between poly-victimization and externalizing behavioral problems in individuals with IDD.
3. **H3:** Peer victimization will emerge as the strongest predictor of both internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems.
4. **H4:** Positive family relationships, particularly father-child relationships, will be negatively associated with internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems, indicating a protective effect.

Methodology

Research Design

The present study employed a **correlational research design** to examine the relationship between poly-victimization and internalizing as well as externalizing behavioral problems among individuals with intellectual developmental disorder (IDD). This design was chosen because it allows the identification of associations between naturally occurring variables without manipulation.

Sampling Strategy

A **purposive sampling strategy** was used to recruit participants for this study. Participants were selected based on the following inclusion criteria:

- Age between 18 and 25 years.
- Formal diagnosis of intellectual developmental disorder (IDD).

- Enrollment in clinical or special education institutions.

Exclusion criteria included:

- Individuals with severe physical disabilities that limited participation.
- Those with acute medical or psychiatric conditions that could confound behavioral assessments.

Participants were recruited from clinical and special education centers across Lahore. Institutional permissions were obtained prior to data collection, and informed consent was sought from legal guardians or primary caregivers.

Sample Characteristics

A total of **120 individuals** diagnosed with IDD participated in the study. The demographic details of the participants are presented below:

Table 2.1
Sample Characteristics N=120

Variables	M	SD	f	%
Age				
18-20			48	40
21-23			47	39.2
24-25			25	20.8
Gender				
Male			87	72.5
Female			33	27.5
Schooling				
Yes			108	90
No			12	10
Family System				
Joint			59	49.2
Nuclear			61	50.8
Father's Occupation				
Unemployed			1	0.8
Private job			55	45.8
Government job			40	33.3
Business			24	20
Mother's Occupation				
Unemployed			77	64.2
Private job			30	25
Government job			13	10.8
Business			0	0
Marital status of Parent				
Lives Together			108	90
Separated			5	4.2
One parent died			6	5
Both died			1	0.8
Any illness(phy/pch)				
Yes			1	0.8
No			119	99.2
Av. Monthly Income	116308.33	320515.59		
Father's Education	12.52	5.608		
Mother's Education	10.72	6.25		
T spent with Father	3.37	2.483		
T spent with Mother	9.14	3.982		

Note: phy= physical, pch=pchological, Av= average and T= quality time.

Instruments

The following standardized instruments were used for data collection:

1. Demographic Information Form

This form gathered participant demographic data, including age, gender, level of IDD, and type of institution. It also collected relevant family

background information.

2. Juvenile Victimization Questionnaire (JVQ) - Adapted Version

The JVQ is a widely used tool for assessing various forms of victimization, including peer victimization, child maltreatment, sexual victimization, and exposure to crime. The adapted version used in this study was culturally modified for Pakistani populations. It demonstrated good reliability in previous studies.

3. Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL) - Adapted Version

The CBCL was used to assess internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems. Caregivers completed the checklist based on their observations. Internalizing subscales included anxiety, depression, and hypersensitivity. Externalizing subscales included aggression, impulsivity, and antisocial behaviors.

Procedure

Institutional permissions were obtained from clinical and special education centers prior to data collection. Legal guardians or primary caregivers of participants were briefed about the study objectives, procedures, and ethical considerations. Written informed consent was obtained from the guardians.

Data were collected individually in a quiet room within the respective institutions. Caregivers completed the questionnaires under the supervision of trained researchers to ensure clarity and accuracy. Data collection was completed over a two-month period.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to the ethical guidelines outlined by the American Psychological Association (APA) and the Centre for Clinical Psychology, University of the Punjab. Key ethical considerations included:

- Informed consent from legal guardians.
- Confidentiality of participant data.
- Right to withdraw from the study at any stage without penalty.
- Sensitivity to the vulnerabilities of individuals with IDD.

Results

This chapter describes the outcome of statistical analyses performed to investigate the relationship in poly victimization and internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems among individuals with intellectual developmental disorder (IDD). The analyses were performed within a systematic sequence to establish the reliability of the tools and the stability of findings.

Reliability Analysis

Reliability refers to the degree to which a measurement instrument consistently measures a construct across its items. Cronbach's alpha (α) was used as the primary measure of internal consistency, with values above .70 generally considered acceptable (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Reliability analyses were conducted for both the Juvenile Victimization Questionnaire (JVQ) and the Measure of Internalizing and Externalizing Behavioral Problems, including all subscales. The results are presented in Table 3.1

Table 3.1
Reliability of Scales and Subscales (N = 120)

Scale/Subscale	k	M	SD	α	Range
Juvenile Victimization Questionnaire (JVQ)	34	91.98	12.64	.704	40-112
Conventional Crime	8	22.08	4.82	.407	9-33
Child Maltreatment	4	11.36	2.86	.152	4-17
Peer Victimization	6	24.41	4.56	.828	7-30
Sexual Victimization	7	12.71	4.07	.649	7-24
Witnessing/Exposure to Violence	9	21.43	4.84	.432	9-35
Meas. External. and Internal. Beh. Prob.	36	114.71	12.68	.690	
Aggression	3	21.43	4.84	.777	5-15
Defiant Behavior	3	12.95	1.96	.030	4-14
Impulsivity	5	8.67	2.23	.435	7-25
Antisocial Behavior	5	14.70	3.67	.307	8-22
Anxiety	7	14.08	3.35	.806	11-35
Depression	7	29.67	4.29	.155	9-27
Hypersensitivity	7	18.83	3.79	.627	6-28

Note. meas.= measure , external.= externalizing ,internal=internalizing, Beh.= behavioral , prob.= problems
k= no. of items in scale/subscale; α = Cronbach's alpha reflects internal consistency.

The overall JVQ demonstrated acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha = .704$), indicating that the scale reliably assessed multiple forms of victimization. The Measure of Internalizing and Externalizing Behavioral Problems also showed acceptable reliability ($\alpha = .690$).

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was conducted to investigate the relationship in the key study variables, poly victimization, internalizing behavior problems, and externalizing behavior problems and their corresponding subscales and values were calculated, given in Table 3.2

Table 3.2

Table showing Pearson correlation coefficients between poly victimization subtypes, behavioral problem subscales and demographics in individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
1 Conv.cri.								.169				.220*	-.040		-.108				
2 Maltreat.	.273**	.388**	.041	.295**	.229*			.135	.222*	.282**		.296**	-.186*			.181*		.050	.032
3 Peer Vict.			.273**	.133	.181*	.294**		.145	.247**	.161	.107	.071	-.060	.034	-.199*	.069	.085		-.060
4 Sex. Vict.				.273**	.133	.181*	.294**	.145	.247**	.161	.107	.071	-.060	.034	-.199*	.069	.085		-.060
5 Exposure.					.496**	.578**		.093	.077	.242**	.622**	.373**	.167	.067	-.085	-.046	.003	-.008	-.006
6 Aggression						.201*	.008	.051	.086	-.075	-.134	-.230*	-.300**	.354**	.368**	.116	.058		-.012
7 Defiant							.263**	.161	.148	.334**	.362**	.307**	.341**	.094	-.294**	.062	.099		-.155
8 Impulsivity								.145	.104	.159	.588**	.123	-.112	.019	.030	-.052	.068	.186*	.006
9 Anti-social												.087	-.064	-.140	-.099			.003	.101
10 Anxiety													.002			.092	.064		
11 Depression														.052	-.052			.103	-.031
12 hypersensit.																			.204*
13 Monthly Inc.																			
14 T w. Father.																			

15 T w. Mother	.028-	.116	-.130
	.037		
16 Family Sys.	-	.029	-.046
	.004		
17 age 1		-.412**	.156
18 age 2			-.132
19 gender male			

Note . conv. cri. = Conventional crime; Maltreat. = Child maltreatment; Peer Vict. = Peer victimization; Sex. Vict. = Sexual victimization; Exposure = Exposure to crime; Anti-social = Antisocial behavior; hypersensit. = Hypersensitivity; Monthly Inc. = Monthly family income; T w. Father = Time spent with father; T w. Mother = Time spent with mother; Family Sys. = Family system , *p< .05, **p< .01, N=120

Peer victimization had the strongest links, showing strong correlations with aggression and anxiety, and moderate correlations with depression, antisocial behavior, and hypersensitivity. Exposure to crime also showed strong positive correlations with aggression, anxiety, and antisocial behavior. Child maltreatment was moderately related to aggression and impulsivity, while conventional crime correlated with aggression, depression, and anxiety. Sexual victimization showed weak and negative correlations with internalizing symptoms, possibly reflecting avoidant coping.

Among covariates, lower family income predicted higher aggression, while greater father-child time predicted lower depression and hypersensitivity. Gender and family structure showed no meaningful associations.

Overall, the findings indicate that poly-victimization is strongly linked to diverse behavioral problems, with effects varying across victimization types

Forward Regression

Forward regression analysis was conducted to investigate the predictive significance of poly victimization on internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems among individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD).

Table 3.3

Table presents the results of forward regression analysis predicting internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems.

Model	Variable	Internalizing Beh. Prob.				Externalizing Beh. Prob.			
		B	SE	β	R ²	B	SE	β	R ²
Model 1	Poly-vict	.305**	.059	.430	.185	.258**	.045	.467	.218

Note. Poly-vict = Poly victimization; Beh.= behavioral; Prob.= problems B = Unstandardized coefficient; SE = Standard Error; β = Standardized Beta; R² = Coefficient of determination. *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001.

The results indicate that poly victimization significantly predicts both internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems. The effect sizes, as reflected by the standardized beta coefficients, suggest a moderately strong predictive relationship in both domains, with slightly greater variance explained for externalizing problems (R² = .218) than for internalizing problems (R² = .185). The results highlight how repeated exposure to varied forms of victimization may overwhelm emotional coping mechanisms, leading to both heightened behavioral problems in individuals with intellectual and developmental disabilities.

To explore these effects in greater depth, regression analyses were also performed on individual subscales of internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems. Results from these subscale-level models are presented in the subsequent Table 3.4 and Table 3.5

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Table 3.4

Table presents the results of forward regression analyses predicting the three subscales of internalizing behavioral problems: anxiety, depression, and hypersensitivity.

Model	Variable	Anxiety				Depression				Hypersensitivity			
		B	SE	β	R ²	B	SE	β	R ²	B	SE	β	R ²
Model 1	Peer vict.	.585 ***	.068	.622	.387	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Model 1	Peer vict.	-	-	-	-	.310 ***	.071	.373	.132	-	-	-	-
Model 2	Peer vict.	-	-	-	-	.292 ***	.069	.351	.190	-	-	-	-
	T with father	-	-	-	-	.390 **	.126	-.255	-	-	-	-	-
Model 1	Exposure.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.319 ***	.081	.341	.116
Model 2	Exposure.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.274 ***	.080	.293	.172
	Sexual vict..	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-.096 .269 **	-.242	.211	

Note. Peer vict. = Peer victimization; T with father = Quality of relationship with father; Exposure = Exposure to crime; Sexual vict. = Sexual victimization.

*p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001.

Forward regression analysis showed that different victimization types predicted different emotional problems. Peer victimization was the strongest predictor of anxiety and depression, indicating that mistreatment by peers increases emotional distress in individuals with IDD. In contrast, a positive father-child relationship predicted lower depression, suggesting a protective effect.

For hypersensitivity, exposure to crime was a significant positive predictor, meaning unsafe or violent environments heighten emotional reactivity. Sexual victimization predicted lower hypersensitivity, possibly reflecting emotional numbing as a coping response.

Table 3.5

Table presents the results of forward regression analyses predicting the three subscales of externalizing behavioral problems: aggression, impulsivity and anti social behavior.

Model	Variable	Aggression				Impulsivity				Anti-social Behavior			
		B	SE	β	R ²	B	SE	β	R ²	B	SE	β	R ²
Model 1	Peer vict.	.249 ***	.032	.578	.334	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Model 2	Peer vict.	.253 ***	.031	.589	.400	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Age 18-21	.684 *	.290	.171	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Model 1	Child mal.	-	-	-	-	.316 **	.114	.247	.061	-	-	-	-
Model 2	Child mal.	-	-	-	-	.301 **	.113	.235	.097	-	-	-	-
	Male	-	-	-	-	1.55 *	.721	.190	-	-	-	-	-
Model 1	Exposure.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.231 ***	.060	.334	.111
Model 2	Exposure .	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	.243 ***	.059	.352	.151
	Separated	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.03 *	1.310	.198	-

Note. B = Unstandardized regression coefficient; SE = Standard error; β = Standardized regression coefficient; R² = Coefficient of determination. Peer vict. = Peer Victimization; Child mal. = Child Maltreatment; Exposure. = Exposure to Crime; Separated = separated parents

*p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001.

Forward regression analyses showed that different victimization types predicted specific externalizing behaviors in individuals with IDD. **Peer victimization** strongly predicted **aggression**, with younger participants more affected. **Child maltreatment** predicted **impulsivity**, and males showed higher levels. **Exposure to crime** predicted **antisocial behavior**, and participants with separated parents exhibited higher antisocial tendencies. The **defiant subscale** showed no significant predictors. These findings indicate that victimization and demographic factors contribute differently to externalizing behaviors, emphasizing the need for targeted assessment and interventions based on trauma type and individual context.

Emerged Model

Figure showing emerged model of the study

Summary of Findings

- The reliability analysis showed that the poly victimization scale had acceptable overall consistency. The peer victimization subscale was highly reliable, while child maltreatment and witnessing violence subscales showed lower reliability. The behavioral problems scale showed moderate reliability, with aggression and anxiety subscales being the most consistent.
- The correlation analysis found that higher levels of poly victimization were significantly associated with more internalizing (e.g., anxiety, depression) and externalizing (e.g., aggression, impulsivity) behavioral problems. Peer victimization showed the strongest and most consistent links with both types of behavioral problems.
- Regression analysis revealed that poly victimization significantly predicted internalizing behavioral problems. Peer victimization was the strongest predictor of anxiety and depression. Exposure to crime was linked to higher hypersensitivity, while sexual victimization was unexpectedly associated with

lower hypersensitivity. A positive relationship with the father was related to fewer depressive symptoms.

- For externalizing behavioral problems, poly victimization also emerged as a significant predictor. Peer victimization predicted aggression, while child maltreatment and being male predicted impulsivity. Exposure to crime and having separated parents were linked to more antisocial behavior. No significant predictors were found for defiant behavior.

Discussion

The present study examined the relationship between **poly-victimization** and **internalizing as well as**

externalizing behavioral problems among individuals with **intellectual developmental disorder (IDD)**. Using standardized instruments with strong reliability, the findings demonstrated significant positive associations between multiple victimization experiences and psychological outcomes. This discussion elaborates on these findings in the context of

existing literature, theoretical frameworks, and cultural considerations.

Poly-Victimization and Behavioral Problems

The results confirmed that individuals with IDD who experienced higher levels of **poly-victimization** exhibited significantly greater internalizing problems such as anxiety, depression, and hypersensitivity, as well as externalizing problems including aggression, impulsivity, and antisocial behaviors. These findings align with international evidence emphasizing the **cumulative effect of multiple victimization experiences** on psychological functioning (Finkelhor et al., 2020; Sterling et al., 2021).

Among the different types of victimization assessed, **peer victimization** consistently emerged as the **strongest predictor** of both internalizing and externalizing behavioral problems. This supports the notion that peer interactions play a critical role in emotional development, especially for individuals with social and cognitive vulnerabilities (Elsaesser et al., 2018; Becker et al., 2021). In collectivistic educational and residential environments, where individuals with IDD frequently interact in shared spaces, peer dynamics become particularly influential.

Child maltreatment and **exposure to crime** also contributed significantly to behavioral outcomes. Consistent with trauma theory (Herman, 1992), chronic exposure to multiple adversities distorts emotional regulation and social cognition, thereby increasing susceptibility to both internalizing and externalizing difficulties. These patterns emphasize the **interplay between environmental stressors and developmental vulnerabilities**, a central idea in ecological-transactional models (Cicchetti & Lynch, 1993). Interestingly, **sexual victimization** emerged as a negative predictor of hypersensitivity within internalizing behaviors. This unexpected finding might reflect **underreporting**, **avoidant emotional coping mechanisms**, or **unique cultural factors** influencing disclosure and caregiver interpretation of sexual trauma. Further qualitative inquiry would help clarify this result in local contexts.

Finally, the **father-child relationship** showed a **protective effect**, being negatively associated with internalizing behavioral problems. Positive paternal involvement is linked with better emotional adjustment and lower depressive symptoms in youth, and this pattern seems to extend to individuals with IDD in collectivist family structures. This finding underscores the importance of family dynamics in shaping psychological outcomes.

Strengths of the Study

This study has several notable strengths:

1. **Novel Context:** It is among the few empirical investigations of poly-victimization in individuals with IDD within Pakistan, contributing culturally contextualized evidence to the global literature.
2. **Comprehensive Framework:** The study integrated **multiple types of victimization** and **two behavioral domains** (internalizing and externalizing), providing a more holistic understanding of psychological outcomes.
3. **Standardized Measures:** Use of adapted, validated versions of JVQ and CBCL ensured reliable assessment.
4. **Analytical Rigor:** The combination of **correlational** and **regression analyses** allowed for identification of both associations and predictive contributions of specific victimization types.
5. **Theoretical Integration:** The study drew upon **trauma theory** and **ecological-transactional frameworks**, strengthening the conceptual basis for interpreting results.

Limitations of the Study

While the findings are significant, several limitations must be considered:

1. **Cross-Sectional Design:** The correlational nature of the study limits causal inferences regarding the directionality of relationships between victimization and behavioral problems.
2. **Caregiver-Reported Data:** Reliance on caregiver reports may introduce **reporting biases**, particularly for sensitive topics such as

sexual victimization.

3. **Sample Specificity:** The purposive sample, limited to clinical and special education settings in Lahore, may restrict **generalizability** to other populations or regions.

4. **Underreporting of Trauma:** Cultural stigma surrounding victimization, especially sexual abuse, may have led to underreporting, potentially influencing findings.

5. **Lack of Longitudinal Data:** The absence of follow-up prevents examination of long-term developmental trajectories or delayed psychological effects.

Future Directions

Building on these findings, future research should aim to:

1. **Adopt Longitudinal Designs:** To better understand causal pathways and developmental changes over time.

2. **Include Multiple Informants:** Combining caregiver, teacher, and self-reports (where possible) can reduce single-source bias and improve data richness.

3. **Expand Sample Diversity:** Including participants from rural areas and different socioeconomic backgrounds will improve external validity.

4. **Explore Qualitative Dimensions:** In-depth interviews and qualitative analyses can illuminate cultural factors affecting disclosure and emotional processing of trauma.

5. **Develop Trauma-Informed Interventions:** Future work should focus on designing and testing culturally appropriate, trauma-informed interventions for individuals with IDD, families, and institutions in Pakistan.

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